

ISic4402

I.Sicily inscription 4402

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

unknown

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halicyae

Place of origin (modern)

Salemi

Provenance

Found by Pace among the foundations of houses (undated) in the predio Chirio, in the vicinity of the early Christian basilica outside Salemi

Coordinates

37.833019, 12.808066

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Salemi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 18 cm

Width 28 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 60 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. ανδρ

2. λλυι

Apparatus

Text of Pace 1916

Translation

Commentary

Pace lists this and one other text-bearing fragment of stone (ISic4403) at the end of his report on the excavation of the basilica at Salemi, indicating that it was found in 'predio Chirio', in the foundations of houses together with several ceramic lamps stamped with a palm. He infers from these that the 'village' surrounding the basilica should likewise be of late antique date (i.e. C4 AD and later). However, ISic4403 is as he notes, inscribed on an architectural block of earlier date, and so certainty is impossible. From the reported text, it seems

likely that the inscription is incomplete, but Pace provides no image and no further information. The current location of this inscription is unknown, and it does not appear to have been reported / noted in any subsequent publication.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Pace, B. 1916. La basilica di Salemi. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 697-736. At 733 no.7

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J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic4402. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381904>